

System of Methodology for Developing Environmental Knowledge and Culture in Students in the Field of Educational Experience

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Abstract: The article gives recommendations on educational and practical task tasks to form environmental knowledge and culture among elementary school students as a result of the work on the educational experiment site.

Keywords: circle, excursion, environment, plants, micropreparations, collections, animals, pen, nodule, bacteria, fungus, stem, seed.

INTRODUCTION

In the article, based on modern scientific data, the first forms of education are the school and its administration, as well as the classification of teaching methods, the level of equipment of the classrooms, the ability to organize the educational process, homework assignments, and extracurricular activities. (circle, public events, individual works), excursions, and the fact that it can be achieved by using modern technologies in teaching. formation of skills and abilities, development of creative abilities, preparation for life allows to be kind to the environment.

These are practical works in the field of educational experience used in natural science lessons. determining and evaluating the quality, choosing the right objects and tools depending on the work content, completing the work and formalizing the result, the method of determining the correctness of the obtained results, self-control methods, educational material short plan, formulating questions, separating the main idea, finding answers to the questions and checking them according to the sample, comparing methods. In the field of educational experience, exhibition tools are extremely important in making education conscious. .

In the process of conducting activities with students, it is necessary to organize environmental education activities in a goal-oriented manner. First of all, it is necessary to form an ecological attitude towards nature, the environment, and all its objects. all work is learned through natural science and life science. Therefore, in the process of teaching science, it is natural to use natural visual aids, collections of plants and animals. Teaching aids: natural, descriptive and It is divided into oral or instrumental. The division of teaching tools into three types is in accordance with the theory of knowledge and the stages of development of students' thinking. It is true. In the educational field, students observe several processes of plants, such as planting plants (from seeds, bulbs, cuttings, nodes, and pods) to flowering and fruiting. Exhibition tools are micropreparations, living or fixed plants, animals, some of their parts, collections, tulips,

herbariums, with which students will get to know directly in the class during educational activities.

With the help of natural visual aids, they are divided into live, dead and fixed visual aids, flat and volumetric types. Natural visual aids are living animals, fish, insects, birds, room Plants, frozen, dried, and fixed visual aids can include tulips, invertebrate animal collections, dried bones, micropreparations, and handouts. In the educational experiment area, live plants and animals should be prepared in advance to be shown during the lesson. When choosing them, attention should be paid to educational morphological features, local conditions and requirements of nature protection should be taken into account. For example (games, lions, stories about plants and ecology.) In addition, one of the natural demonstration tools of practical methods in the training field is micropreparations. They are small organisms, bacteria, fungi, single-celled animals, represents the cellular structure of plants. All students should acquire the skill of preparing micropreparations. Many natural exhibition tools are necessary for conducting laboratory and practical training.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

In the field of experience, students will be able to perform a number of operations, such as mutual comparison of objects and crops in nature, observation, acquaintance with each animate and inanimate object of nature, their analysis, analysis, synthesis and generalization. The most interesting activity is During the school year, students develop an environment in which their affection for the environment and their care for it lead to the formation of environmental awareness and love. A pedagogue should be able to create a system of teaching methods while conducting training. Therefore, the results of the field trips, materials, and observations strengthen the lessons in the field of educational experience. Young naturalists come out with their own drawings and documents during the field trips, and write a lot of information about what they have learned. After the excursion, students prepare reports with pictures and diagrams. All inclusive forms of the lesson are called "Excursion Method".

Pupils work in the school site and learn about nature, different types of plants and animals, their life forms, external structure, the differences between cultivated and wild plants. they form ideas about agronomic methods, perceptive abilities and skills in a certain system of working with them. Field works teach students to work hard, be kind to their friends, take care of plants, take care of them not to give, to be careful, public skills, aesthetic feelings and the formation of an attitude to preserve nature by growing plants, teaches to cultivate skills.

Students work together with the pedagogue on the school site, and a number of activities are organized outside the school classroom: harvest day, garden day, bird day, plant day, ecology day. plants: fields, fields, trees, shrubs, grasses, (one-year, perennial, two-year) flowers, animals should be studied in sections. and a place is allocated for conducting experiments on them. Fields of land are cultivated for conducting experiments. Of course, when conducting each experiment, when passing the topics of grades V-VI, from general biology to grade IX, "Reproduction and individual development" The basics of genetics and selection are reinforced by re-reading the topics by the teacher.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Various types of plants are planted and grown in the training field, including the germination and reproduction of vegetable plants. More than 120 cultivated species are known. 90 species belonging to 10 families are widespread. Vegetable crops are cabbages (cabbage, turnips, radishes, radishes, etc.), cruciferous vegetables (carrots, celery, parsley, dill, etc.), sauerkrauts (beets, etc.), squashes (cucumbers, watermelons, melons, pumpkins), tomatoes (tomatoes, eggplant, pepper), legumes (mushrooms, peas, beans), cruciferous vegetables (lettuce, etc.), onions (onions, garlic, onions), sorghums (carob, sorrel) are divided into botanical families.

Onions and spikelets belong to monocotyledonous plants, and the rest to dicotyledonous plants. Vegetable crops are divided into one-year (cucumber, tomato, pepper, eggplant), two-year (carrot, cabbage, onion, garlic, etc.) and perennial (scallion, sorrel, etc.) crops according to the type of duration of growth and development.

According to the productive organs (edible part) into 5 groups: root vegetables (carrots, beets, turnips, radishes, radishes), bulbs (onions, garlic), fruit vegetables (tomatoes, eggplants, peppers, cucumbers, watermelons, melons, etc.), leafy vegetables (cabbage, dill, spinach, celery, parsley), leguminous vegetables (green peas, beans, chickpeas). In two-year vegetable crops, in the 1st year, the organs of the crop used for food ripen. In the 2nd year, they give seeds (onions, garlic, cabbage, etc.). Most vegetable crops are heat-loving, soil-fertility and moisture-demanding vegetable crops are grown in all agricultural regions of the world.

Planting crops - placing plant seeds in the upper layer of the soil for harvesting; one of the main agricultural activities. The methods of planting crops are chosen taking into account the requirements of crops for feeding area, light and moisture, crop care, first of all, working between the rows with the help of mechanization. Scattering is the simplest method; in this case, the seed sown by hand falls on the soil and is placed at different depths with the help of a harrow or trowel.

Row planting (row spacing 10-25 cm, often 15 cm) is used mainly in the cultivation of grain crops. The row seeder throws the seed at the bottom of the field and buries it with soft soil, the seed germinates evenly. Narrow row planting (between rows 7-8 cm) is used more than row planting when planting cereals, alfalfa, flax, etc. In this case, the seeds are evenly placed on the field. Wide row planting (more than 45 cm between rows) is used for sowing crops (corn, sugar beet, sunflower, marigold, root crops, etc.). When planting in the form of a ribbon (ribbon), the wide rows between the ribbons are alternated with narrow rows (carrots, radishes, etc. are planted this way). In nest planting, several seeds are placed in each nest. In the spot sowing method, seeds are sown individually at a certain distance from each other. In regions with severe cold and little snow, the method of sowing is used for autumn crops; the seed is planted at the bottom of the ground, the snow accumulated on the ground prevents the sprouted seedlings from freezing.

Cultivation of plant bushes and seedlings (tomato, eggplant, cabbage, fruit and ornamental trees) and then planting in the main place is part of the seedling method.

Depending on the time of sowing, crops are divided into spring (spring crops), autumn (autumn crops), summer (for second harvest), late autumn (for early harvesting of seeds). There is an optimal planting time for each plant. In Central Asia, wheat, barley, flax, sugar beet, alfalfa, and sunflower are early spring crops. The time of planting late spring crops is determined by soil and air temperature. Autumn crops (winter wheat, alfalfa, etc.) are planted in the conditions of Uzbekistan in late October - early November. Crops planted before the onset of frost develop and strengthen to a certain extent. The depth of sowing seeds depends on the biological characteristics of plants and the mechanical composition of the soil. The larger the seeds, the deeper they are planted (for example, corn 6-8 cm, grain crops 4-6 cm, etc.). The seeds are sown shallower than on light, sandy and loamy soils with a heavy mechanical composition. When planting, soil moisture is also taken into account (the seed should not settle in the dry layer of the soil).

Sometimes, in order to protect seeds from birds and strong winds, the depth of planting (for example, corn, peas) is increased. importance is determined based on the plant's demand for the nutrition area, planting time, methods, etc. When preparing the seeds for planting, their quality, purity, and fertility are checked. A plan is drawn up on each farm, showing the planting units, the time of the work and the order in which it will be carried out. When assessing the

quality of sowing, its timely implementation, sowing of seeds at the same depth, the rate of sowing seeds, rows and correctness are checked.

DISCUSSION

The work done in the field of educational experience for elementary school students will change their attitude towards nature more, so it is necessary to involve them more in the work in the field of experience. We would have started the formation of culture.

CONCLUSION

Based on the following information, it should be mentioned that all the work, exercises, and methods performed in the educational field include measures to develop the child's environmental knowledge and culture. Therefore, we pedagogues study more natural sciences. We should pay special attention to the child's attitude towards the animate and inanimate nature in the field of experience.

Used literature

1. Ж.О.Толипова .А.Т.Гофуров.Биология укитиш методикаси.
2. Q.Haydarov, S.Nishonova Tabiatshunoslik asoslari va bolalarni atrof-tabiat bilan tanishtirish. T.O'qituvchi. 1992.
3. Yusupova P.A. Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarga ekologik tarbiya berish.
4. Ekologiya biosfera va tabiatni munhofaza qilish.Ergashev.
5. И.Холлиев.А.Икромов “Экология.”Тошкент –Мехнат -2001.йил.